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A Sociological Academic Analysis of Postmodern Criminology Approach and Peaceful Criminology Response in the Framework of Political Science

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Abstract

Criminal psychologists are specialists that aid law enforcement in the process of capturing criminals, conducting interviews with such criminals, and acquiring a better understanding of the offender's state of mind by interrogating the offender about the crime they have done. Criminal psychologists are those who assist law enforcement in apprehending criminals. Most people generally identify the term "criminal psychology" with Hollywood films such as "Silence of the Lambs," however the term "criminal psychologist" refers to the individuals themselves. It is concerned with the study of anthropology and examines not only the factors that drive someone to commit a crime, but also the consequences of crime, including the thoughts and feelings a criminal experiences both before and after committing a crime. In addition, it looks at the factors that drive someone to commit a crime, including how they feel about themselves and how they feel about others. In addition to this, it looks at the motivations that drive a person to commit a crime when they are in the process of committing a crime. In addition to this, it investigates the conditions that lead an individual to commit a crime while they were in the act of committing that crime. The term "criminal psychology" may refer to an extremely broad range of various concepts, depending on the context in which it is used. Even currently, there is no definition that can be agreed upon as being broadly recognized by most people. It is feasible to categorize it as a part of the scientific community that assists investigative organizations in carrying out their responsibilities in a more effective manner by using psychological understanding on the topic at hand. This is a goal that is

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attainable by using the role that psychological understanding performs in our society today. The field of research known as criminal psychology investigates not only the thoughts, will, and motivations of criminals, but also the thoughts, will, and acts of individuals who participate in illicit conduct. This academic subfield has only been around for a relatively little period across the whole of human history. It was not until the latter half of the 19th century that instruction in this sphere was first made available at academic institutions like colleges and universities. Yet, for the whole of the investigation, valid offender profiling procedures were used by the investigators.

Keywords: *Criminology, Postmodern Criminology, Peaceful Criminology, Social Psychology, Criminal Psychology*

Introduction

Hugo Munsterberg, a German psychologist, is often regarded as the person who was responsible for launching the subfield of criminal psychology. It is well documented that he carried out these activities in the early decades of the 20th century. His publications from the 19th and 20th centuries continue to be given considerable consideration by psychologists working in the field today. From the beginning of the 20th century, there has been an increase in the amount of involvement that criminal psychologists have in the whole process of preventing and punishing criminal activity. The beginning of this pattern may be located around the turn of the century. As a direct consequence of this, the job that criminal psychologists do today is regarded in very high respect in every industrialized nation around the globe. Everyone formerly thought that inheritance was the one and only factor that contributed to criminal behavior; however, as time went on, everyone learned that this was not the case, and that this assumption was incorrect. Once upon a time, everyone held the belief that criminal conduct was simply inherited. For instance, the genetic predisposition theory states that a kid is more likely to grow up to be a criminal if his or her mother suffers from schizophrenia symptoms and the child's father has a criminal record that includes a conviction for rape or murder. This estimation is based on the reality that the father of the kid had a prior criminal record. On the other hand, if the youngster is provided with the appropriate education, he will not grow up to be a harmful member of society. Hence, a person's genetic make-

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up, in addition to the environment in which they grew up, may have a substantial effect on the development of a person's predisposition to participate in criminal conduct. This inclination can also be influenced by the environment in which a person was raised.

Method and Research Methods

The likelihood that an individual would steal greatly rises when that individual is subjected to constant and violent conflict for the sole purpose of obtaining sufficient food to ensure his survival. When individuals are unable to locate enough food to sustain themselves, they have the option of stealing it. Financial troubles It is not difficult for an individual who has been bullied because of their social and economic standing to turn around and bully other people and battle with society when they feel as if they have no other alternative. This is how they speak about themselves if someone tells them that someone has a poor social rank.

Cesare Lombroso is considered as the "creator of modern criminology" by most people, and this acceptance is very close to being universal. When it comes to gaining an understanding of criminal conduct, the most prevalent school of thought throughout the latter part of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century was Lombroso's concept of the "born criminal." This theory was first proposed in the middle of the 19th century. According to his idea of criminal atavism, those who have never been convicted of any crime and those who have committed crimes in the past may be differentiated from one another based on the physical qualities that they possess. These characteristics include a sloping forehead, ears of an abnormally large size, extraordinarily long limbs, and less sensitivity to pain than average. According to this hypothesis, individuals who have not been convicted of any crime and those who have been guilty of a crime may be differentiated from one another based on the physical qualities that they possess.

Since he was one of the first people to make the attempt to properly classify offenders according to age, he was a pioneer in the discipline of criminology.

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Figure - Categorizing criminals

As a direct result of his achievements, we have every reason to refer to him as a pioneer. He discovered, via an analysis of these shared characteristics, that the source of the motivation to engage in criminal action is the same in each instance. Because of this, he arrived at the conclusion. This comprehension served as the foundation for his book "The Guilty Man," which he authored and first released for publication in the year 1876. Over the course of his inquiry, Lombroso spoke with a total of 383 Italian inmates and gathered information from them. Upon the completion of his investigation, he arrived at the conclusion that there are three distinct groups of criminals now active in the globe. There were two categories of people who committed crimes in the world: those who were born evil and immoral, and those who suffered from mental illness and committed atrocities. Both categories of lawbreakers have been documented in different parts of the globe. There were lawbreakers who fell into both categories all around the globe. In addition to this, he carried out study and came up with several unique characteristics of an individual's outward look. A face that is asymmetrical, flaws and abnormalities in the eyes, ears that are an odd size, and

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other traits that are like these are instances of this. 3 Both forensic medicine and criminal psychology place a significant emphasis on investigating these challenges as their primary research topic. This is since these challenges are the origin of all our actions. This concentration is owing to the discovery that the way in which our brain functions is affected by a wide range of circumstances, including those of a psychological and social origin.

The enormous number of categories that are used to categorize crime adds another layer of complexity to the already challenging task of psychologically studying criminal conduct. Wortley contends that it is impossible to draw significant conclusions about a person's criminal character since they may be found guilty of doing an act today but not tomorrow. An effort was made by Robert Agnew to explain his definition of crime, which included this uncertainty. He is of the opinion that "acts that produce deplorable injury, are condemned by society, and/or are not accepted by the state" should constitute the definition of crime. According to this point of view, the focus has switched away from illegal actions of the past and toward a broader variety of risky behaviors shown by humans (Durrant, 2018).

The news media, social media, the government, as well as our own personal experiences, all contribute to the fact that everyone of us has a unique view on the criminal underground. While there is a connection between all these factors, the media has the largest effect on how huge audiences and society as a whole view criminal activity. The media coverage often concentrates on sensationalized events rather than honestly presenting criminal situations, such as property crimes or theft, which are underrepresented in newspapers. This is because the media coverage of criminal circumstances is underrepresented in newspapers. On the other hand, significant crimes like rape and murder are often included in the reporting of many news channels (Howitt, 2006).

According to the most recent data from the International Criminal Registry, the number of crimes that were recorded rose by 1.3% despite a marginal decline in the crime rate per population, which went from 388.6 in 2017 to 383.5 in 2018. This change occurred between the years 2017 and 2018. In 2018, there were an increased number of complaints of economic crime, cybercrime, suicide, and crimes committed against women compared to 2017. This is in line with the results of previous crime surveys (NCRB, 2018). If they are actively working in this profession, criminal

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psychologists should be aware of recent developments that have occurred in the criminal justice system on both the national and local levels (Howitt, 2006). It is possible to determine this using a variety of methods, such as conducting surveys of the general population and offenders, surveys of victims, police reports or criminal records, statistics on people who are currently incarcerated, and information on crimes for which a defendant has been found guilty in court. In contrast to criminology, which focuses on criminal behavior, criminal activity, and responses to crime, psychology examines specific characteristics and influencing factors, combining parts of criminology and psychology. Knowledge and experience are required for precise interpretation of data because each resource examines specific characteristics and factors, combining parts of criminology and psychology (Newburn, 2013).

There have been a variety of approaches taken in defining what exactly is meant by the term "criminal psychology." "the field of applied psychology dealing with the collecting, assessment, and presenting of evidence for forensic purposes," according to Gudjonsson and Haward's (1998) definition of applied psychology. This line of reasoning demonstrates the connection that exists between criminal psychology, the judicial system, and the process of inquiry. Yet, after criminals have served their time, they are sent to criminal psychologists for evaluation and participation in rehabilitation programs. According to the work of an American psychologist called Wrightsman (2001), "criminal psychology" may be defined as "the application of psychological knowledge or processes to a job filled by the legal system." This is a more precise definition of the field.

Literature Data

Since criminal psychologists can participate in all aspects of the criminal justice system, even post-execution, it is necessary to provide a full description of all the functions that criminal psychologists play. There is still much disagreement over how precisely one should define criminal psychology. There is a lot of overlap between the fields of forensic psychology, legal psychology, and criminal psychology, therefore the names are sometimes used interchangeably. Despite this, there is absolutely no crossover between these fields and criminal psychology. The study of how theory is applied in criminal investigations, how to understand the psychological factors that contribute to criminal behavior, and how to rehabilitate offenders are all topics that fall under the

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purview of forensic psychology, which is a field of psychology that focuses on the psychological aspects of legal processes (Bull et al., 2009). The professional practice of forensic psychology often includes contributions from psychologists trained in all branches of psychology, including clinical psychology, developmental psychology, social psychology, cognitive psychology, and social psychology. The concerned psychologist makes use of his experience in the legal field to address legal and administrative matters (Vaya, 2015). Although the two branches of study are quite similar, criminal psychology places a greater emphasis on the offender than forensic psychology does. Despite this, the final determination of guilt is made by the criminal justice system, which takes into consideration not only the immediate circumstances of the case but also the offender's time spent in court or behind bars. In addition to the cultural setting of the crime, this also has a role. In this light, one may claim that the functions played by forensic psychologists and criminal psychologists are extremely comparable to one another. The primary contrast lies in the fact that forensic psychology may be used in both civil and criminal law settings.

Development of criminal psychology over time

The origins of the psychology of crime may be found in a variety of academic disciplines, including criminology, psychology, and sociology. Articles on lie detection based on concealed emotional indicators may be found in the field of criminal psychology, which is where it all originated. Some of these publications date back to the time of Charles Darwin. Although face muscles cannot be deliberately manipulated, the author contends that a miserable person may nevertheless regulate or control their bodily motions. These concepts were used in Paul Eckman's method of detecting deception by observing the subject's facial expressions. Sir Francis Galton's creation of a word association test to assist in lie detection is the beginning of forensic and criminal psychology in the United Kingdom. In this scenario, the evaluator will say a term that is connected to the crime, and then they will observe the suspect's response very attentively (Matte, 2007). Although many of Wilhelm Wundt's students and colleagues have had significant impacts on the field of criminal psychology, the establishment of the psychology laboratory in 1875 by Wilhelm Wundt serves as an important touchstone in the development of forensic science and criminal psychology. This is even though Wundt was one of the pioneers in the field. In 1985, James McKeen Cattell, a former student at Wundt, carried out a methodical, controlled laboratory

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assessment of human memory to evaluate the credibility of eyewitness evidence. This study investigated individual variations in the ways in which the environment affects the veracity of eyewitness testimonies. Alfred Binet in France and William Stern in Germany both conducted research that were quite like one another. In the year 1905, Carl Gustav Jung conducted a word association test on a criminal suspect who was in Germany. Then came along Hugo Münsterberg, an applied psychologist who was a pioneer in the realm of law when it came to putting psychological principles into legal language. In his work published in 1908 titled "On the Witness Stand," he posed questions about the function of psychological research in judicial procedures as well as how psychologists may supply objective facts to support testimony and evidence. When he accomplished this, psychology was still in its infancy as a profession and had not yet been acknowledged as having a valid role in the legal system. Lionel Haward, who teaches psychology at the University of Surrey in the United Kingdom, provided an explanation for his thinking behind the psychologist's participation in the court proceedings. He carried out an inquiry to verify the truthfulness of a police officer's assertion that he had accurately recorded the license plate information for a motorbike that was traveling at a high rate of speed. Interestingly, not even one of the over one hundred professional observers who took part in the experiment was successful in correctly identifying the license numbers.

[The Field of Criminal Psychology Expanded Significantly As World War II Ended](#)

In 1960, Hans Eysenck offered a complete explanation of criminal conduct to the scientific community. The decades of the 1970s and 1980s witnessed tremendous institutional expansion and disciplinary improvement in the fields of forensic science and criminal psychology. According to a proposition made by Royo in 1996, the creation of relevant university courses, the establishment of associations, the publication of specialized books and journals, the formal institutionalization of the field as part of the formal justice system, and the publication of specialized books and journals are all ways that can help the development of the field.

[The Importance of Criminal Psychology in Understanding Criminal Behaviors](#)

Meetings and organizations within the academic world are very important to the growth of a field since they encourage research partnerships across different universities and institutions on regional, national, and even worldwide levels. The American Psychological-Legal Association

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was established in 1969 with the goal of serving this function. After that, he was a vital contributor to the expansion of the 41st Department of Psychology and Law of the American Psychological Association (APA), which the division eventually merged with in 1981.

The British Psychological Association founded the Department of Forensic Psychology in 1977; before to that, it was known as the Department of Criminological and Legal Psychology. In recent years, forensic psychology has become more important in the legal system. This section is responsible for managing legal publications. Psychiatry, Psychology, and Law had its first issue published by the Australian and New Zealand Psychiatric, Psychological, and Law Associations in 1993 and 1972, respectively. Both organizations were responsible for founding the magazine. Before the inaugural psychology and law conference, which took place in Maastricht, the Netherlands, in 1988, members of the European Psychology and Law Association started getting together in smaller groups. A later and even more significant event resulted in the establishment of the European Psychology and Law Society in Nuremberg (VandenBos).

Vocational training

In several nations, students may pursue postgraduate courses in the fields of psychology and law. Several educational opportunities are available in each country:

“US over thirty, United Kingdom about twenty, Australia about nine, Germany four, Spain four, Russia four, Canada four, Sweden twenty, United Kingdom about twenty, USA over thirty, and England about twenty”

The next generation will benefit greatly from education that is both comprehensive and conveniently accessible across all areas of study. There are, on the other hand, publications that are devoted only to the dissemination of research in the domains of forensic science, criminal psychology, and civil psychology. Just 47% of all citations came from the top 68 publications that were referenced the most often, which included 15 journals that were specifically devoted to legal psychology (Howitt, 2006).

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In the early nineteenth century, the study of criminal psychology was still in its infancy as a fresh new academic discipline that was only beginning to take shape. Thematic Apperception Test, Draw a Person, Bender Gestalt 26, SP Sahni and N. Phakey Tests, Henry Murray, The Word Association Test, Sentence Completion Test, and Rorschach Inkblot Test, Carl Jung, and other projective tests by SP Sahni, N. Phakey et al., have been used in forensic psychological testing of criminal suspects since 1985. These tests were developed by SP Sahni, N. Ph (real case studies). This made it much simpler, between the years 1985 and 1988, to get psychological information that was helpful when interviewing suspects.

To examine suspects, a combination of a therapeutic approach and investigative knowledge was used, which ultimately led to the creation of forensic interrogation techniques. As a result of the development of criminal psychology, clinical psychologists now have administrative authority and the ability to evaluate a defendant's appearance in court, as well as family court reconciliation and victim rehabilitation in both civil and criminal cases. In addition, criminal psychologists now can conduct forensic interviews. Hypnosis, expression analysis, updated polygraph exams, psychological testing, and narcoanalysis are some examples of the more empirical approaches that have superseded older heuristics devised to match the purposes of study. Other methodologies include narcoanalysis (Vaya S. L).

Professor Lionel Haward, who is one of the pioneers of criminal psychology in the United Kingdom, was the first person to identify the function that psychologists fulfill when they are professionally engaged in criminal cases. The purpose of providing law enforcement and probation agencies with access to this information is to assist them in developing a deeper comprehension of the subject's psychological make-up. It is possible to make a request that the suspect be tested by a psychologist to decide whether the suspect is permitted to face trial, whether the accused can understand what is going on in court, or whether the accused is mentally stable. The findings of these evaluations will have an impact on the operation of the criminal justice system as well as the processes followed in courts.

In this capacity, the subject matter expert takes part in research efforts to provide evidence that is free from prejudice on the problem at hand. This involves conducting investigations utilizing

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psychological tests to offer an opinion or further information to assist the decision making of the courts (for example, the possibility of a person accurately identifying a person driving on a highway, at a distance, in the dark).

On the other hand, it is possible that the court will ask psychologists to submit the findings of previous study that has been conducted on the topic.

Actuarial

In this context, statistics are used to provide the court with information on the likelihood that a given event will take place, such as the likelihood that a criminal would commit another offense. In this scenario, the court could discuss the pre- or post-sentencing report with a psychologist to get some advice on how to proceed. In this capacity, the psychologist may advise law enforcement on how to proceed with decisions that might have an impact on an investigation. A criminal psychologist can provide information that may be useful to the investigation when it comes to the process of building a criminal profile. Investigating a single suspect and gaining a knowledge of criminal conduct are both components of having a solid grasp of criminal psychology.

Cross-examination witness in court

A psychologist may serve in this capacity by providing advice to the departments of probation, court, jail, and police. As was previously said, the function of psychologists extends to include all circumstances in which their involvement in the legal system is required. This encompasses the whole range of circumstances. The aid that a criminal psychologist provides to a criminal investigation is the single most significant function that they are responsible for doing. Professor Laurence Alison of the University of Liverpool stated that it would be beneficial for the police to have access to the knowledge that psychologists have to provide to aid them in their job. The process of accumulating, aggregating, and assessing the data obtained may be made more efficient with the help of criminal psychologists. This assistance may come in a variety of ways, such as assisting in the creation of offender profiles or offering advice on how to conduct interviews more successfully with victims, offenders, and witnesses. They are also able to assist in the development of data-driven algorithms that may be used in the real world to prioritize suspects. As a result of

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this, it should come as no surprise that law enforcement receives significant and ongoing help from criminal psychologists (Durrant, 2018).

Crime Analysis

Techniques with a psychological focus are often used while doing intelligence analysis. Law enforcement agencies often hire criminal psychologists to conduct study and analysis of crime data. These criminal psychologists frequently aid law enforcement agencies in the course of their job. Most of the time, a crime analyst's job is trying to connect separate crimes by making use of patterns of the offender's conduct that have been extracted from the crime scene or stated by victims of the crimes.

"Which patient would be guilty?" This is the secondary question that needs to be answered. "Which came first, crime or mental illness?" This is one of the most important questions doctors ask. (Which happened first: criminal act or mental illness?)

Danger Associated with Repeated Violations

A person is said to have committed recidivism if they have had a negative experience or continue to participate in undesirable behaviors after being punished for their previous behavior. This pattern of conduct may be thought of as an activity. An individual who participates in illicit acts on a consistent basis is an excellent illustration of this kind of conduct. This takes place when the convicted criminal is at risk of committing another violation, and maybe additional offenses in the future as well. It has been shown that a substantial decrease in the rate of recidivism may be accomplished by giving individuals who are at a medium or high risk of committing another crime the greatest priority in terms of the allocation of resources. Those who are judged to be repeat offenders are subject to this rule.

Discussion and Analysis

Transferring the offender to a new facility after his sentence has been served is one of the most successful tactics for lowering the rate of recidivism; this is one of the most effective strategies for reducing the rate of recidivism. Because of this, the offender will have a decreased propensity to

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conduct other crimes in the future since he will have a greater understanding of the consequences that will follow from the acts he does as a direct result of this. After serving their term, the offender will be required to move to a new location, which will serve as the impetus for them to reinvent themselves and begin a new chapter in their lives. Since the setting in which the individual is humiliated, in addition to the location where the crime was done, will serve as a trigger for him and prevent him from evolving into a different person, respectively. Modifying a person's surroundings is one of the most successful tactics for minimizing the risk that a person would participate in criminal conduct again. It is also one of the most difficult things to do. The use of an individual's intrinsic motivation, which arises when a person reaches a certain level of introspection and calmness, may be another method for reducing the likelihood that a perpetrator will commit the same crime again. This is because intrinsic motivation arises when a person achieves a certain level of introspection and calmness. It is possible for a person to make use of their inherent motivation in situations when they are compelled to make changes. Moreover, showing empathy for the offender is a beneficial strategy that may be used in this work. Showing empathy toward the offender does not indicate that the person is approving the offender's actions in any way.

The important role that the surrounding environment plays as a catalytic component in the process

A change in environment helps criminals live a better life than a new episode because with the change in their environment, they are no longer reminded of their difficult past and they are relieved of the guilt they lived together; it also reduces the risk of recidivism. The environment always acts as a catalyst to change the mindset of criminals. People can start a new chapter of their lives and live better lives because of changes in their surroundings because, because of the change in their environment, they are no longer reminded of their challenging past and are under less strain. Due of the shift in their surroundings, they are no longer confronted with memories of their troubled past, and as a result, they are liberated from the repercussions of it.

On the other side, relocating to a new location implies that he will have the chance to begin his life again and will have a clean slate on which to build his future. The outcome of this situation will be favorable. Because of this, he will have the opportunity to direct his life in a new direction. So,

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a change in one's environment has the potential to operate as an essential and substantial driver in the healing process for a person who has been previously convicted of a crime. This is because of the way that environments may influence a person's thoughts, feelings, and behaviors. There are a lot of hypotheses and theories that attempt to figure out what drives people to engage in criminal behavior.

The five-factor model developed by Costa and McCare, which was previously developed We have entered the era of contemporary personality studies because of this group of principles, which are also referred to as the Big Five on occasion. Extraversion is a personality characteristic. It is characterized by having the traits of being outgoing and socially self-confident, which is how it is classified.

Compatibility

Other qualities, such as warmth, cuteness, and charity, contribute to an individual's overall pleasantness. Both a short fuse and a predisposition toward hostility are included in this facet of a person's personality. When seen in its whole, each of these characteristics contributes to the bigger, more comprehensive trait that is referred to as compatibility. The capacity to control one's impulses and act in ways that are in line with what is expected of them in each social environment is an illustration of a personality attribute known as conscientiousness. Another example of conscientiousness is the ability to be punctual. One way to describe conscientiousness is as the propensity to control or moderate one's impulses. There is a connection between neuroticism and the source of a person's energy, as well as the way individuals interact with one another and with the world around them. On the other hand, openness may be interpreted in a variety of ways, such as intellect or creativity. The concept of "openness" relates to the distinct mental lives and experiences that everyone has.

Eysenck's Pencil Model

Everything may be reduced to the following three components in this way: If you want to be more outgoing, you should participate in activities that demand you to communicate and collaborate with a variety of others. When a person's thoughts and feelings become so warped that they are no longer in touch with the objective facts that are going on around them, that person is said to be

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suffering from the severe mental disease known as psychosis. The onset of psychosis may be influenced by a wide variety of circumstances and circumstances can play a role in the development of psychosis. Carl Jung, a psychologist, is credited with developing the concept of neuroticism, which refers to the propensity to experience unfavorable feelings such as worry or depression over an extended length of time. Those who have a high level of neuroticism also tend to be highly persistent, which contributes to the act of breaking the law becoming a habit that is constantly reinforced (increasing the degree to which one thinks in a predetermined way, while at the same time reducing the degree of guilt). It is challenging for a person to conform to social norms and conditioning when they have high degrees of extraversion in addition to psychosis since this combination makes it more difficult for them to catch up. This, in turn, raises the likelihood that the individual will engage in illegal behavior. It was found that the p (psychosis) component of Eysenck's pencil model is connected to the big five model that was developed by Costa and McCare. This turned out to be an unexpected finding. A person's emotional disposition as well as their intellectual capabilities are additional aspects that may be taken into consideration when attempting to ascertain the possibility that a person would conduct a criminal act. Glenn D. Walters's theory is that what he has to say about the topic is that a person's traits, in addition to the circumstances of their surroundings, are a factor in a person's choice to engage in an unlawful conduct. This is what he has to say about the topic. The author Glenn D. Walter's work, "Personality Theory of Context," was honored with five different honors. The collective name for these different ways of thinking is "cognitive styles." A person's cognition is the ultimate result of the cognitive styles they choose to use. In the same way that a criminal lifestyle is the result of a choice the criminal makes because of the conditions in their environment, a person's cognition is the result of the choices they make regarding their cognitive styles. Those who engage in criminal activities as a way of life often suffer from cognitive deficits or issues with their thinking, both of which contribute to the conduct of these people.

There are some significant exceptions, but the great majority of policy-related research in criminology is written at a very high level of abstraction or has a micro-structure, employing theories such as neo-liberalism or governmentality to describe the policy-making process. The level places more of an emphasis on analyzing the results of policies than it does on looking into

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how such policies are formulated. There may be an exception to any of these two rules, but as a rule, the work that is done in the field of policy-related criminology is written in one of these two styles. This dynamic may be seen in action in the discourse over the Youth Criminal Justice Act that took place between Hogeveen (2005) and Doob and Spratt (2006). (YCJA). Doob and Spratt (2006) point out that Hogeveen's argument that establishing a "discursive category" of "punishable young offender" results in demands for a "new criminal ethics" to safeguard the public from the hazards of juvenile crime is what leads to these calls for a "new criminal ethics." This is substantiated either by the language of the law or by the results of the legislation in terms of the number of young people that are incarcerated. Doob and Spratt point out that the reason for this is because neither the words of the legislation nor its consequences for youth levels led to later demands for a "new ethic of retaliation," according to Hogeveen. Doob and Spratt point out that this is because neither the words of the legislation nor its consequences for youth levels (2005: 73). Participants in the policy process contribute to the development of new policies in juvenile justice.

Using research approaches that are based on institutions, political scientists have been able to give the type of intermediate analysis that is often absent in policy studies guiding the criminal justice system. This opened a significant vacuum in information that might be filled by political scientists. Before continuing to highlight some examples of how such strategies have been used successfully in different criminal justice challenges, it would be appropriate to begin by providing a brief overview of the institutionalist perspective. This would be done before continuing to highlight some examples of how such strategies have been used in different criminal justice challenges. The new institutionalist set of values, in general, places a strong emphasis on the following three important roles that institutions play in the process of policy formation, and these responsibilities are as follows:

According to Hiebert (2002), the Supreme Court concluded that the DNA database did not infringe on any of the rights and freedoms guaranteed by the Charter of Rights and Freedoms. According to the findings of Hiebert (2002), the institutional shift that occurred in 1982 with the enshrinement of the Bill of Rights had a substantial effect on the formulation of public policy.

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This finding may be attributed to the fact that the Bill of Rights was enshrined. This modification became effective once the Human Rights Act was written into the statutes. This is not just because courts are granted the right to declare laws and acts of government employees (such as the police) unlawful, but also since the Ministry of Justice looks to be unconstitutional. Both factors contributed to this result. This is the situation since the courts are granted the authority to declare unlawful both legislation and the behavior of government authorities (such as the police). This was one of the elements that helped contribute to the decision to place a greater focus on rights-based terminology. But it compensates for its lack of parsimony by providing an explanation of policy-making that is, in some respects, more realistic than the explanations provided by other theories. The institutionalist method that Pal (2000) and Hiebert (2002) used has been criticized for veering away from a distinct description of the phenomenon being studied. The problem of how public authority is exercised (and where its limits are set) might be a particularly hard one in the realm of criminal justice. To address this question, which may be especially challenging to respond to owing to the nature of the subject, political scientists can gain an advantage from the training they get in their field. This topic will get a more in-depth examination in the next sections.

Criminals, as a matter of course, think that Robert K. Murton's theory about the offender is accurate, as a matter of course, as a matter of course. They are under pressure from society to seek objectives that are socially acceptable, and this crime is the outcome of a conflict between a person's aims and the tactics they employ to attain that conflict. Society places this pressure on them. There is a fear that this disagreement may result in illegal activity.

In our society, if accusations are made against us, we are presumed to be guilty as soon as the claims are made, regardless of whether the charges are true. The unfavorable connotation associated with it follows us everywhere we go. Yet, the method in which our society functions run on the presumption that an individual is guilty unless it is proved otherwise. Moreover, even after being acquitted, an individual is still branded and classified as guilty even if they are proven innocent. This is since, in our culture, it is generally accepted that individuals are always guilty

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until they can establish their innocence. One of the foundational tenets of natural law is known as the presumption of innocent, and it states that an individual's guilt cannot be deduced from the activities that they do.

The Criminal Code is not gender neutral; rather, it is gender-based, as can be seen in the black laws outlined earlier, which cover various crimes of humiliation, voyeurism, stalking, and similar offenses. This can be observed in the black laws. This is shown by the fact that the Criminal Code covers charges such as voyeurism, stalking, and humiliating women's modesty, all of which fall within the category of similar acts. Nonetheless, even though the legislation is intended to provide women greater freedom, it still permits considerable forms of aggressive conduct. This presents a particularly difficult challenge when because women are statistically more likely to be the victims of violence in the home.

Although these depictions in the media get certain parts of a criminal psychologist's work correct, they do a terrible job of presenting the numerous other functions that a criminal psychologist could play. These images, for instance, do not do a very good job of demonstrating how a criminal psychologist could investigate a crime. They do not demonstrate, for instance, how the aid of a forensic psychologist might be advantageous to the victims of a crime. There are certain parts of the work of a criminal psychologist that are depicted accurately, but there are also other aspects of the job that are not portrayed correctly. Someone who makes their living in criminal psychology is in no way representative of the typical or typical example of an individual.

The field of criminal psychology investigates the thought processes that lie underneath criminal conduct. The commission or omission of an act by the offender may be the basis for a criminal charge; nevertheless, this conclusion is heavily dependent on the specifics of the circumstance (Mclaughlin & Munice, 2001). However, the definition of crime is not fixed; rather, what constitutes a criminal act depends not only on the place and time when the behavior was committed, but also on the pre-existing cultural norms of that place and time. In other words, the definition of what constitutes a criminal act changes depending not only on the place and time, but also on the cultural norms. In other words, the definition of a criminal conduct is not only dependent on the location and time the action was performed, but also on the social practices and

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traditions of the culture in issue. may change (Newburn, 2013). In certain nations, for instance, homosexuality, prostitution, and marital rape, in addition to the use of a broad range of substances such as cannabis, are seen as acceptable forms of conduct, yet in other countries, such activities are deemed to be illegal. In several other nations, the usage of marijuana is against the law.

If the same item was stolen from both victims, if the same sort of weapon was used, or if another murder was committed nearby, the police will be able to utilize all this information to establish if the same individual or a particular gang was responsible for both killings. This enables a more targeted examination while also lowering the amount of time and effort that is wasted.

Creating Criminal Profiles

To precisely identify the offender, crime profiling often makes use of data gathered at the site of the incident as well as information provided by witnesses and victims. A profile of this kind provides answers to a variety of questions that are interconnected, such as the offender's age and gender, as well as whether the crime was planned. SP With the material that has been supplied, the investigating agencies of Sahni and N. Phakey are able to create a list of likely suspects. Recently, the public's attention has been drawn to the use of criminal profiling methods created by criminal psychologists, and this attention has been drawn to both faked and actual high-profile instances. Although because of this, the disciplinary profile will become more well-known, the undulating presentation will undercut the research that supports it in some respects.

Questioning Suspects and Victims

The accumulation of trustworthy evidence to establish what took place at the location of the crime is the most essential part of any investigation. Interrogation methods need to be correct if investigators are to acquire precise information from witnesses and victims without introducing prejudice or coercing their testimony. When interrogating potential suspects, you should use a very different set of methods than those you use when asking potential witnesses. Experiments have shown evidence that implies interviewers may purposefully or inadvertently change eyewitnesses' memory of events. [Citation needed] As a consequence of this, the kind of interview that is performed and the way it is carried out are both very essential aspects of the case. When it comes to consulting and educating law enforcement officials on how to conduct interviews with suspects

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or witnesses, psychologists play a very essential role. The investigative authorities could also seek the assistance of psychiatrists to learn how to properly interview witnesses or suspects who are known to be especially difficult, such as young children or elderly people.

Conclusion

Because of the complexity of the cognitive and mental aptitude concerns at play in some court processes, the help of a criminal psychologist is required. It is common practice to solicit the thoughts and perspectives of relevant specialists whenever possible; nevertheless, the specifics of how this procedure is carried out might vary from one jurisdiction to the next. For instance, if a court in a European country need the expert's opinion or certain information, the court may on occasion summon him or her as a witness. Both the prosecution and the defense in the United States and the United Kingdom will look for expert witness to support their respective positions. In recent years, an increasing number of people have been consulting psychologists for guidance on a variety of issues, such as the reliability of eyewitness testimony, the efficacy of various interview techniques, the psychometric or clinical evaluation of a suspect or witness, and the image extraction procedures that were utilized during the investigation. In nations such as Australia, Canada, and the United Kingdom, criminal psychologists play a key part in activities connected to the examination, rehabilitation, and management of criminals both while they are incarcerated and after they are released from their sentences. Counseling inmates who are distressed because of their isolation in prison or other stresses such as bullying and trauma or working with criminals to lessen their risks of reoffending, are two examples of the kind of activities that fall under this category. Before and after the sentence of the criminal, an assessment of the offender's potential of committing more crimes, danger of causing damage to himself or others, and mental health requirements is carried out. The findings of these investigations may also be used in the planning stages of evacuating convicts and arranging for their rehabilitation. Psychologists provide operational input to monitor the behavior of an offender who is deemed to pose a high risk to society. In addition to providing management and counseling support for the implementation of treatments to reduce risk, psychologists provide this support for the implementation of treatments. In addition to this, criminal psychologists create risk assessment studies for the courts, teach

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probation officers and convicts, and bring criminals' welfare needs to the attention of the court. In this sense, there is a significant amount of further work that must be done for the literature in Turkey.

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